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Kinetic Parameters from TG Analysis of Copper-Pyrrole-2-thiocarboxamide Complex

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THE rate of thermal decomposition is determined by the rate of one or more of these stages. Sometimes the rate-determining stage at the beginning of the pyrolysis may lose its significance and later another stage can take its place.

The decomposition rate of a TG curve can be defined as $-d\alpha/dt$, where α stands for the fraction of the initial compound undergoing reaction. In isothermal conditions it may be presumed that the reaction rate is dependent only to the fraction reacted,

$$-\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K\alpha^n$$

where n is the order of reaction and K the specific rate constant. The specific rate constant depends upon the temperature by the expression,

$$K = A.e^{-E/RT}$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor, E the activation energy and R the gas constant.

Experimental

An electrobalance with a recorder operating at 1 mV full scale was used for obtaining the thermograms. A chromelalumel thermocouple placed 3–4 mm below the sample holder, the platinum boat (2 mm × 8 mm dia) was used for recording the sample temperature. A heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ was employed and chart speed was maintained at 600 mm h⁻¹. Calculations were carried out from

a single TG curve for the second stage of decomposition of the complex around 190°. The initial stage corresponded to the elimination of coordinated water.

Preparation of the sample: A green precipitate of copper complex corresponding to molecular formula CuL.H₂O was obtained by mixing the ethanolic solutions of the ligand with cupric chloride in the molar ratio of 1 : 1.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic parameter of the complex have been calculated by both Freeman and Carroll method and Zsako method.

Freeman and Carroll¹ suggested a linear relationship between $\Delta \log \frac{dw}{dt} / \Delta \log W_r$ and $\Delta T^{-1} / \Delta \log W_r$, where $W_r = (W_0 - W)$ and W_0 is weight loss at completion of reaction, W the total weight-loss upto time t and T the absolute temperature. The intercept $-x$ of the straight line plotted from the evaluated values for the equation indicates the order of reaction and the slope indicates the energy of activation E_a to $E_a/2.3R$. The reaction order and the activation energy of the compound have been evaluated as 1.0 and 35.69 kcal mol⁻¹ for the second transformation stage under consideration.

These values were compared with the method of Doyle² as modified by Zsako³. Doyle's equation for TG curve is

$$g(\alpha) = \frac{ZE_a}{Rq} p(x)$$

where Z is frequency factor, E_a the activation energy, R the gas constant and q the heating rate. The value $g(\alpha)$ is a certain function of α and

$$\alpha = \frac{W_0 - W}{W_0 - W_t}$$

where W , W_0 and W_t are the actual, initial and final weights of the sample respectively. The $g(\alpha)$ is calculated for various order of decomposition from the equation,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(1 - \alpha)^b$$

where b is the order of reaction. For $b = 0$ $g_0(\alpha) = \alpha$, for $b = 1$, $g_1(\alpha) = \ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - \alpha}\right)$ and for $b = 2$,

$$g_2(\alpha) = \left(\frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha}\right).$$

The values of B_0 , B_1 and B_2 have been calculated in the present case from the equations given herein with the help of the data for $g(\alpha)$ and $-\log p(x)$ at different temperatures. B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are the constancy of the difference $\log(\alpha) - \log p(x)$ for zero, first and second order reactions respectively, which provide information to suggest

a quantitative method for determining the apparent activation energy consistent with a given function $f(\alpha)$.

$$b=0; B_0 = \log \alpha - \log p(x)$$

$$b=1; B_1 = \log \left(\ln \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \right) - \log p(x)$$

$$b=2; B_2 = \log \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right) - \log p(x)$$

and the value of $g(\alpha)$ are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Temp. °C	W mg	$\log \alpha$	$\log \left(\frac{1}{1-\alpha} \right)$	$\log \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \right)$
1.	190	4.50	-1.634	-1.629	-1.624
2.	200	4.45	-1.332	-1.322	-1.311
3.	210	4.30	-0.934	-0.907	-0.880
4.	220	4.05	-0.633	-0.577	-0.518
5.	230	3.75	-0.429	-0.332	-0.227
6.	240	3.20	-0.202	-0.004	0.227
7.	250	2.65	-0.053	0.332	0.880
8.	260	2.50	-0.020	0.486	1.310

$$W_0 = 4.55 \text{ mg}, W_t = 2.440 \text{ mg.}$$

For quantitative evaluation of the value of E_a , the arithmetical mean of B_0 , B_1 and B_2 have been calculated and also the standard deviation δ for all the three pre-supposed order of reactions. The δ is obtained from the relation,

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{(B_i - \bar{B})^2}{r}}$$

where B_i is any value, \bar{B} their arithmetical mean and r the number of values. The various values for the corresponding B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2

B_0		B_1		B_2	
E_a	δ_0	E_a	δ_1	E_a	δ_2
24	0.102 8	32	0.057 3	42	0.147 2
26	0.099 1	34	0.043 3	44	0.135 8
28	0.112 0	36	0.069 7	46	0.136 1

It is apparent from Table 2 that the standard deviations are minimum if the first order reaction is accepted, and the value for δ is minimum for $E_a = 34.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and corresponds to 0.0433. The value of the arithmetical mean, i.e. \bar{B} corresponds to 17.554.

The frequency factor Z for the solid state kinetics is evaluated as $\log Z = 17.319$ by means of the relation,

$$\log Z = \bar{B} + \log Rq - \log E_a$$

where q is the heating rate and R the gas constant.

The apparent activation entropy, ΔS^\ddagger is calculated as +9.88 e.u. from relation,

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = 2.303 \log (Zh/kT)$$

The value for T in this equation is the temperature $T_{1/2}$ at which the weight-loss is half the total loss during the step of transformation under consideration.

The values for E_a with order of reaction $b=1$ by Freeman and Carroll and Zsako are 35.69 and 34.00 kcal mol^{-1} respectively. The values for E_a , b calculated by the procedures mentioned earlier seem to be in good agreement with each other and thus may be utilised in the study of solid state reaction mechanism.

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Kinetic Analysis of Consecutive First Order Reaction: Oxidation of Succinic Acid Dihydrazide by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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A number of oxidants have been employed in the kinetic studies of the oxidation of hydrazides¹. But no attempts have been made so far to study the kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic dihydrazides by alkaline hexacyanoferrate. Here, we report the kinetic analysis of the oxidation of succinic acid dihydrazide by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

Succinic acid dihydrazide, prepared by known method² was crystallised from ethanol and used as such. Potassium hexacyanoferrate and other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used. All the kinetic runs were carried out in a thermostated ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) water-bath. Reaction rates were determined by estimating remaining amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) spectrophotometrically using a DDR Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer at 420 nm. The absorption due to